

**PRINCIPLES AND FEATURES OF THE COMMUNICATIVE
APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH**

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Abstract: This article deal with various methods of teaching English in oral form within a certain situation. We investigate the methodology known as Communicative Language Teaching or CLT and explore its origins and evolution since it was first proposed in the 1960s, and how it has influenced approaches to language teaching today. It is crucial, students knowing the ways of communicating with other people, when learning a second language. We focused on the need to form an integrated approach in the preparation and realization of classes and tasks for the effective development of students' oral speech skills.

Keywords: Communicative language teaching, communicative approach, proficiency, social language, authenticity, productively and receptively.

Introduction

Communicative language teaching (CLT) is an approach to the teaching of second and foreign languages that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language. It is also referred to as "communicative approach to the teaching of foreign languages", "communication-oriented teaching" or simply the "communicative approach".

"Communicative" is a word, which has dominated discussions of teaching methodology for many years. Although in a monolingual English language classroom, real communication in English is impossible. In communicative methodology, we try to be more communicative. That is to say, even though it may be impossible to achieve

real communication, we should attempt to get closer to real communication in classrooms [1].

Its origins are many, in so far as one teaching methodology tends to influence the next. The communicative approach could be said to be the product of educators and linguists who had grown dissatisfied with the audiolingual and grammar-translation methods of foreign language instruction. They felt that students were not learning enough realistic, whole language. They did not know how to communicate using appropriate social language, gestures, or expressions; in brief, they were at a loss to communicate in the culture of the language studied.

Materials and Methods

Communicative approach to language teaching first appeared in print in the field of the English Language Teaching (ELT) some decades ago. Communicative language teaching began in Britain in the 1960s as a replacement to the earlier structural method, called "Situational Language Teaching". This was partly in response to N. Chomsky's criticisms of structural theories of language and partly based on the theories of British functional linguists, such as D. Hymes and the writings of D. H. Ecroyd on speech acts [3].

Interest in and development of communicative-style teaching mushroomed in the 1970s; authentic language use and classroom exchanges where students engaged in real communication with one another became quite popular.

In the intervening years, the communicative approach has been adapted to the elementary, middle, secondary, and post-secondary levels, and the underlying philosophy has spawned different teaching methods known under a variety of names, including notional-functional, teaching for proficiency, proficiency-based instruction, and communicative language teaching.

Influenced by S. Krashen communicative approach was further developed during the 1980s and 1990s and was concentrated on the communicative functions of language. Classrooms were characterized by attempts to ensure authenticity of materials and meaningful tasks [5].

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) emerged as the norm in second language and immersion teaching. As a broadly-based approach, there are any number of definitions and interpretations, but the following interconnected characteristics offered by D. H. Brown provide a useful overview:

1. Classroom goals are focused on all of the components (grammatical, discourse, functional, sociolinguistic, and strategic) of communicative competence. Goals therefore must intertwine the organizational aspects of language with the pragmatic.

2. Language techniques are designed to engage learners in the pragmatic, authentic, functional use of language for meaningful purposes. Organizational language forms are not the central focus, but rather aspects of language that enable the learner to accomplish those purposes.

3. Fluency and accuracy are seen as complementary principles underlying communicative techniques. At times fluency may have to take on more importance than accuracy in order to keep learners meaningfully engaged in language use.

4. Students in a communicative class ultimately have to use the language, productively and receptively, in unrehearsed contexts outside the classroom. Classroom tasks must therefore equip students with the skills necessary for communication in those contexts.

5. Students are given opportunities to focus on their own learning process through an understanding of their own styles of learning and through the development of appropriate strategies for autonomous learning.

6. The role of the teacher is that of facilitator and guide, not an all-knowing best over of knowledge. Students are therefore encouraged to construct meaning through genuine linguistic interaction with others.

The communicative approach was developed mainly in the context of English Second Language (ESL) teaching. The question must be asked, however, how universal can its application be? A. Malamah-Thomas points out that "one can relatively easily reach a fair level of communication in English, which has a relatively simple morphology (e. g. simple plurals with `s', no adjectival agreement, no gender

markers, etc). Neither is mastery of the highly irregular orthography of English a priority in an oral communication approach” [7].

Results

CLT is usually characterized as a broad approach to teaching, rather than as a teaching method with a clearly defined set of classroom practices. As such, it is most often defined as a list of **general principles or features**. One of the most recognized of these lists is David Nunan's five features of CLT:

1. An emphasis on learning to communicate through interaction in the target language.
2. The introduction of authentic texts into the learning situation.
3. The provision of opportunities for learners to focus, not only on language but also on the Learning Management process.
4. An enhancement of the learner's own personal experiences as important contributing elements to classroom learning.
5. An attempt to link classroom language learning with language activities outside the classroom [4].

These five features are claimed by practitioners of CLT to show that they are very interested in the needs and desires of their learners as well as the connection between the language as it is taught in their class and as it used outside the classroom. Under this broad umbrella definition, any teaching practice that helps students develop their **communicative competence** in an authentic context is deemed an acceptable and beneficial form of instruction.

In the classroom CLT often takes the form of pair and group work requiring negotiation and cooperation between learners, fluency-based activities that encourage learners to develop their confidence, role-plays in which students practice and develop language functions, as well as judicious use of grammar and pronunciation focused activities.

As such, the aim of the communicative approach to language teaching is to focus on real conversations about real subjects so that communication is the engine of

learning. This communication may lead to explanation, but that this in turn will lead to further communication.

Communicative approach is based on ten principles.

1. Interactivity: the most direct route to learning is to be found in the interactivity between teachers and students and amongst the students themselves.

2. Engagement: students are most engaged by content they have created themselves

3. Dialogic processes: learning is social and dialogic, where knowledge is co-constructed

4. Scaffolded conversations: learning takes place through conversations, where the learner and teacher co-construct the knowledge and skills

5. Emergence: language and grammar emerge from the learning process. This is seen as distinct from the 'acquisition' of language.

6. Affordances: the teacher's role is to optimize language learning affordances through directing attention to emergent language.

7. Voice: the learner's voice is given recognition along with the learner's beliefs and knowledge.

8. Empowerment: students and teachers are empowered by freeing the classroom of published materials and textbooks.

9. Relevance: materials (e. g. texts, audios and videos) should have relevance for the learners.

10. Critical use: teachers and students should use published materials and textbooks in a critical way that recognizes their cultural and ideological biases.

Today, we see our primary aim as teaching the practical use of English for communication with native speakers and others.

Conversation is seen as central to language learning within the communicative approach framework, because it is the fundamental and universal form of language and so is considered language at work. Since real life conversation is more interactional than it is transactional, this approach places more value on communication that promotes social interaction. Communicative approach also places more emphasis on a

discourse-level (rather than sentence-level) approach to language, as it is considered to better prepare learners for real-life communication, where the entire conversation is more relevant than the analysis of specific utterances.

Discussion

Communicative approach considers that the learning of a skill is co-constructed within the interaction between the learner and the teacher. In this sense, teaching is a conversation between the two parties.

Communicative competence is a main objective in communicative teaching.

Communicative competence is a term in linguistics which refers to a language user's grammatical knowledge of syntax, morphology, phonology and the like, as well as social knowledge about how and when to use utterances appropriately.

Dell Hymes coined the term in 1966, reacting against the perceived inadequacy of Noam Chomsky's distinction between competence and performance.

To address N. Chomsky's abstract notion of competence, D. Hymes undertook ethnographic exploration of communicative competence that included "communicative form and function in integral relation to each other". The approach pioneered by D. Hymes is now known as the ethnography of communication [2].

Debate has occurred regarding linguistic competence and communicative competence in the second and foreign language teaching literature, and scholars have found communicative competence as a superior model of language following D. Hymes' opposition to N. Chomsky's linguistic competence. This opposition has been adopted by those who seek new directions toward a communicative era by taking for granted the basic motives and the appropriateness of this opposition behind the development of communicative competence [4].

Language teaching in the United States is based on the idea that the goal of language acquisition is communicative competence: the ability to use the language correctly and appropriately to accomplish communication goals.

The desired outcome of the language learning process is the ability to communicate competently, not the ability to use the language exactly as a native speaker does. In the early stages of language learning, instructors and students may

want to keep in mind the goal of communicative efficiency: learners should be able to make themselves understood, using their current proficiency to the fullest. They should try to avoid confusion in the message (due to faulty pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary); to avoid offending communication partners (due to socially inappropriate style); and to use strategies for recognizing and managing communication breakdowns.

Through the influence of communicative language teaching, it has become widely accepted that communicative competence should be the goal of language education, central to good classroom practice. This is in contrast to previous views in which grammatical competence was commonly given top priority.

Communicative competence is made up of four competence areas: linguistic, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic.

➤ Linguistic competence is knowing how to use the grammar, syntax, and vocabulary of a language. Linguistic competence asks: What words do I use? How do I put them into phrases and sentences?

➤ Sociolinguistic competence is knowing how to use and respond to language appropriately, given the setting, the topic, and the relationships among the people communicating. Sociolinguistic competence asks: Which words and phrases fit this setting and this topic? How can I express a specific attitude (courtesy, authority, friendliness, respect) when I need to? How do I know what attitude another person is expressing?

➤ Discourse competence is knowing how to interpret the larger context and how to construct longer stretches of language so that the parts make up a coherent whole. Discourse competence asks: How are words, phrases and sentences put together to create conversations, speeches, email messages, newspaper articles?

➤ Strategic competence is knowing how to recognize and repair communication breakdowns, how to work around gaps in one's knowledge of the language, and how to learn more about the language and in the context. Strategic competence asks: How do I know when I have misunderstood or when someone has misunderstood me? What do I say then? How can I express my ideas if I do not know the name of something or the right verb form to use?

Thus, we can see that the modules in this section identify eight aspects of communicative competence. They are grouped together in two groups of four:

Linguistic aspects:

- Phonology and orthography
- Grammar
- Vocabulary
- Discourse (textual)

Pragmatic aspects:

- Functional aspect
- Sociolinguistic aspect)
- Interactional skills
- Cultural framework

The linguistics aspects of communicative competence are those that have to do with achieving an internalized functional knowledge of the elements and structures of the language.

Phonological competence is the ability to recognize and produce the distinctive meaningful sounds of a language, including:

- consonants
- vowels
- tone patterns
- intonation patterns
- rhythm patterns
- stress patterns
- any other suprasegmentally features that carry meaning.

Grammatical competence is the ability to recognize and produce the distinctive grammatical structures of a language and to use them effectively in communication. Grammatical competence as defined by Noam Chomsky would include phonological competence [2].

Lexical competence is the ability to recognize and use words in a language in the way that speakers of the language use them. Lexical competence includes

understanding the different relationships among families of words and the common collocations of words.

Learners learning English need to be able to recognize the concept of chair and what makes it different from a stool, a sofa, or a bench. They also need to know that a chair is a piece of furniture, and that there are various kinds of chairs, including easy chairs, deck chairs, office chairs, and rocking chairs and so on. They also need to understand how chair is now used in an extended sense for what used to be termed a chairman, especially when referring to a woman, as in Julie Wright is the chair of the committee.

Discourse competence is used to refer to two related, but distinct abilities. Textual discourse competence refers to the ability to understand and construct monologues or written texts of different genres, such as narratives, procedural texts, expository texts, persuasive (hortatory) texts, descriptions and others. These discourse genres have different characteristics, but in each genre, there are some elements that help make the text coherent and other elements, which are used to make important points distinctive or prominent.

Learning a language involves learning how to relate these different types of discourse in such a way that hearers or readers can understand what is going on and see what is important. Likewise it involves being able to relate information in a way that is coherent to the readers and hearers.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we can say that communicative language teaching is best considered an approach rather than a method. It has been developed in the 1960s as a replacement to the earlier structural method, called "Situational Language Teaching".

Situational Language Teaching was no longer felt to reflect a methodology appropriate for the seventies and beyond. CLT appealed to those who sought a more humanistic approach to teaching, one in which the interactive processes of communication received priority. The rapid adoption and implementation of the communicative approach also resulted from the fact that it received the sanction and

support of leading British applied linguists, language specialists, publishers, as well as institutions, such as the British Council.

Main features of CLT is the emphasis on learning to communicate through interaction in the target language, the introduction of authentic texts into the learning situation, etc. The main aim of CLT is developing communicative competence, which includes linguistic, sociolinguistic, discourse and strategic competence.

Teaching and classroom materials today consequently make use of a wide variety of small group activities. In addition, it can be concluded that the ability of the teacher to properly organize the lesson and expertly choose a particular form of training depends largely on the effectiveness of the educational process.

All these techniques involve students in the learning process and are based on the intercourse between objects of interaction.

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